

Reactions of Nickel Ions with Nitroso-Naphthols II. Formation and Dissociation Kinetics of Some Nickel Complexes.

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The dissociation kinetics of NiL (HL = 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol-6-sulphonate, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol-3,6-disulphonate and 2-nitroso-1-naphthol-4-sulphonate) in aqueous acidic solution are reported as functions of ionic strength and temperature and Arrhenius parameters deduced. The kinetics of formation of NiL (HL = 2-nitroso-1-naphthol-4-sulphonate and 1-nitroso-2-naphthol-3,6-disulphonate) are also reported at 25°C. In both the dissociation and formations the behaviour of the -3,6-disulphonate complex is unusual. It is suggested that an unusually strong proton bridge may exist between the substituents in the -2- and -3- positions.

THE chelating ligands 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, 2-nitroso-1-naphthol and their sulphonated derivatives are powerful complexing agents. The previous study¹ included the kinetics of the dissociation reaction in equation (1)

where HL was 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, 2-nitroso-1-naphthol, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol-3,6-disulphonate and 2-nitroso-1-naphthol-4-sulphonate. The present report deals with the new ligand 1-nitroso-2-naphthol-6-sulphonate, examines the effects of ionic strength on the dissociation kinetics of the nickel complexes of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, 1-nitroso-2-naphthol-3,6-disulphonate and 2-nitroso-1-naphthol-4-sulphonate. Formation kinetics of the nickel complex of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol-3,6-disulphonate and 2-nitroso-1-nitroso-4-sulphonate are also reported.

Experimental

Freshly prepared glass distilled water was used throughout. 1-nitroso-2-naphthol and 1-nitroso-2-naphthol-3,6-potassium disulphonate and 2-nitroso-1-naphthol were prepared and purified as reported previously¹. 1-nitroso-2-naphthol-6-sulphonate was prepared from sodium 2-naphthol-6-sulphonate by nitrosation with sodium nitrite following the method of Mäkitie and Saarinen².

The solutions of nickel(II) were prepared from reagent grade Ni(NO₃)₂ · 6H₂O, and were standardised by EDTA—ZnSO₄ titration³ with eriochrome black T as indicator. Lithium nitrate was recrystallised from water. Concentrated nitric acid was diluted by a factor of 2 and then aerated for 2 hours to remove any dissolved oxides of nitrogen. The acid was stored in an amber coloured pyrex bottle. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade.

Kinetics Studies

A Durrum stopped flow reactor was used in the absorbance mode. The output signal was stored in a Biomation 802 transient recorder and later recorded on a Hewlett-Packard 7001 AM XY recorder. Temperature was controlled by circulating water from a thermostated bath. The reactions were followed at 450 nm and the rate constants obtained by least squares fits using the data from the XY recorder traces and a Hewlett-Packard 9100B programmable calculator. In the dissociation kinetics studies one drive syringe contained Ni²⁺ and HL in the ratio 100 : 1 { [HL] = 10⁻⁵ M } to ensure formation of the NiL complex only. The other contained nitric acid of known concentration.

In the formation studies, one of the drive syringes was filled with Ni²⁺ solution (5 × 10⁻³ M) and the other contained ligand (5 × 10⁻⁵ M). Both Ni²⁺ and ligand solutions were buffered either with 2,6-lutidine or with 2,4,6-collidine or quinaldine as appropriate. After each kinetic run the effluent from the stop syringe of the stopped-flow apparatus was collected in a small beaker and the pH of the solution was measured immediately with an Orion 801A ionalyser.

At least three replicate determinations were obtained under a given set of reaction conditions. Reproducibility in the observed rate constants was about ±5%.

Results

The dissociation of Ni (1-nitroso-2-naphthol-6-sulphonate). The pseudo-first order rate constants, *k*, obtained for this reaction are given in Table 1 as a function of [H⁺] and temperature. The rate data in Table 1 tend to a limiting value at high [H⁺]. As shown later, whatever the detailed mechanism chosen the plots 1/*k* vs 1/[H⁺] give an intercept (1/*k_d*) where *k_d* is a unimolecular dissociation rate constant and slope (1/*C*) where *C* is a collection of constants dealt with more fully below. Plots of 1/*k* vs 1/H⁺ are in Figure 1.

TABLE 1—PSEUDO-FIRST-ORDER RATE CONSTANTS (sec⁻¹) FOR THE ACID DISSOCIATION OF THE Ni(1-NITROSO-2-NAPHTHOL-6-SULPHONATE) COMPLEX.

[HL]₀ = 1 × 10⁻⁵ M, I = 0.5 M (LiNO₃).

	15°C					
10 ² [H ⁺]	5	10	20	25	40	50
k _{obs}	38.5	77.8	124	143	173	210
	20°C					
10 ² [H ⁺]	5	10	20	25	40	50
k _{obs}	51.8	96.6	162.3	192	258	308
	25°C					
10 ² [H ⁺]	1	10	19	30	40	50
k _{obs}	14.5	128	115	246	400	433

At 25°C :

$$1/k = 8.69 \times 10^{-4} + 6.814 \times 10^{-4} \{1/[H^+]\} \quad (4)$$

Standard deviations in intercept and slope are 7.6 × 10⁻⁵ and 1.87 × 10⁻⁶ respectively.

The values of k_a and C obtained from these equations are in Table 2.

TABLE 2—VARIATION OF k_a AND C WITH TEMPERATURE FOR Ni (1-NITROSO-2-NAPHTHOL-6-SULPHONATE)

	15°	20°	25°
k _a	417	617	1150
C	872	1201	1468

Figure 1. The variation of 1/k_{obs} with 1/[H⁺] for the acid dissociation of the Ni (1-nitroso-2-naphthol-6-sulphonate) Complex.

Linear least square fits gave equations (2) – (4).

At 15°C :

$$1/k = 2.398 \times 10^{-3} + 1.147 \times 10^{-3} \{1/[H^+]\} \quad (2)$$

Standard deviations in the intercept and slope are 4.09 × 10⁻⁴ and 4.27 × 10⁻⁵ respectively.

At 20°C :

$$1/k = 1.620 \times 10^{-3} + 8.323 \times 10^{-4} \{1/[H^+]\} \quad (3)$$

Standard deviations in intercept and slope are 7.82 × 10⁻⁶ and 8.15 × 10⁻⁶ respectively.

These temperature dependences are reproduced by Arrhenius type equations (5) and (6).

$$k_a = 5.243 \times 10^{15} \exp(-17,295/RT) \quad (5)$$

$$C = 5.023 \times 10^9 \exp(-8,903/RT) \quad (6)$$

with coefficients of correlation of 0.990 and 0.993 respectively.

The Dissociation of Ni (1-nitroso-2-naphthol) : The kinetic data already reported for Ni (1-nitroso-2-naphthol) at 0.1 M ionic strength were extended at 0.5 M ionic strength as given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANT, (sec⁻¹) FOR THE ACID DISSOCIATION OF THE Ni (1-NITROSO-2-NAPHTHOL) COMPLEX. I=0.5 M (LiNO₃)

[H ⁺]	0.01	0.03	0.05	0.08	0.10	0.02	0.30
k _{obs} (15°C)	18.8	45.0	63.8	87.0	94.9	127	147
k _{obs} (20°C)	22.7	58.8	83.4	121	136	168	204
k _{obs} (25°C)	45	105	162	220	285	40	346

The limiting rate with respect to [H⁺] is clearly shown in the last row of Table 3. Treating the data in Table 3 as previously the following equations are obtained :

$$\text{At } 15^\circ\text{C} ; 1/k = 5.695 \times 10^{-3} + 4.775 \times 10^{-4} (1/[H^+]) \quad (7)$$

Standard deviations in the intercept and slope are 2.1×10^{-4} and 5.2×10^{-6} respectively.

$$\text{At } 20^\circ\text{C} ; 1/k = 3.568 \times 10^{-4} + 4.048 \times 10^{-4} (1/[H^+]) \quad (8)$$

Standard deviations in the intercept and slope are 1.4×10^{-4} and 3.6×10^{-6} respectively.

$$\text{At } 25^\circ\text{C} ; 1/k = 2.045 \times 10^{-3} + 2.035 \times 10^{-4} (1/[H^+]) \quad (9)$$

Standard deviations in the intercept and slope are 2.1×10^{-4} and 5.1×10^{-6} respectively.

The values of k_a and C obtained from equations (7)–(9) are in Table 4.

TABLE 4—TEMPERATURE EFFECTS ON THE ACID DISSOCIATION OF Ni (1-NITROSO-2-NAPHTHOL) AT 25°C. IONIC STRENGTH = 0.5 M

Temp. °C	15	20	25
k _a	176	280	489
C	2094	2470	4914

The temperature variation of k_a is reproduced by equation (10).

$$k_a = 2.892 \times 10^{15} \exp (-17,435/RT) \quad (10)$$

with a coefficient of correlation of 0.998.

The Dissociation of Ni (1-nitroso-2-naphthol-3,6-disulphonate): Whereas all the nickel complexes show a levelling off in the dissociation rates as [H⁺] is increased the effect is much reduced with the 1-nitroso-2-naphthol-3,6-sulphonate compound as shown in Table 5.

TABLE 5—DISSOCIATION OF Ni COMPLEX OF 1-NITROSO-2-NAPHTHOL-3, 6-DISULPHONATE : EFFECT OF ACID CONC. AT 0.5 M IONIC STRENGTH AND 25°C

[H ⁺] M	k _{obs} sec ⁻¹	k _{obs} / [H ⁺]
0.011	7.02	638
0.049	28.2	576
0.094	54.2	577
0.20	106.4	532
0.295	150.6	511
0.40	191.4	479

The last column in Table 5 shows a decrease in $k_{obs}/[H^+]$ of only 25% for a 36 fold increase in [H⁺] in contrast with the obvious limiting behaviour shown by the 6-sulphonate complex for example.

These data treated in the same way as above give equation (11).

$$1/k = 1.818 \times 10^{-3} + 1.545 \times 10^{-3} (1/[H^+]) \quad (11)$$

where the intercept and slope have standard deviations of 4.5×10^{-4} and 1.19×10^{-5} respectively. The values of k_a and C under the present experimental conditions are therefore 550 and 647 respectively.

Ionic Strength Effects: The observed rate constants at various ionic strengths, adjusted with lithium nitrate at fixed [H⁺] are shown in Table 6.

TABLE 6—IONIC STRENGTH EFFECTS ON THE RATE OF THE DISSOCIATION REACTIONS AT 25°C. k_{obs} IN SEC⁻¹.

[Ni] = 5 × 10 ⁻⁵ M ; [HL] = 5 × 10 ⁻⁵ M Ni (1-nitroso-2-naphthol-6-sulphonate) [H ⁺] = 0.01 M ; Z _A Z _B = 0					
I	0.02	0.02	0.06	0.08	0.10
k _{obs}	19.5	21.0	21.3	21.7	22.4
Ni (1-nitroso-2-naphthol) [H ⁺] = 0.02 M Z _A Z _B = +1					
I	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.08	0.10
k _{obs}	47.6	51.0	54.9	57.9	60.2
Ni (1-nitroso-2-naphthol-3, 6-disulphonate) [H ⁺] = 0.04 M ; Z _A Z _B = -1					
I	0.04	0.05	0.07	0.08	0.09
k _{obs}	21.1	20.7	21.7	20.5	20.6
Ni (2-nitroso-1-naphthol-4-sulphonate) [H ⁺] = 0.01 M ; Z _A Z _B = 0					
I	0.02	0.04	0.10	0.10	0.5
k _{obs}	28.0	27.8	28.1	28.1	28.1

The Formation Reactions: The observed rate constants for the formation of two nickel/nitroso-naphthol complexes over a range of pH values are in Table 7.

TABLE 7—PSEUDO-FIRST ORDER RATE CONSTANTS FOR FORMATIONS 25°C, I=0.5 M

Ni (2-nitroso-1-naphthol-4-sulphonate)		Ni (1-nitroso-2-naphthol-3,6-disulpho-nate)	
pH	k_{obs} /sec ⁻¹	pH	k_{obs} /sec ⁻¹
3.90	11.6	3.20	3.28
5.17	13.0	3.66	5.59
5.39	15.5	3.72	5.90
5.58	20.5	4.06	7.20
5.67	25.4	4.50	9.70
5.79	30.2	5.10	13.80
5.82	30.2	6.08	34.8
5.85	30.1	6.36	45.5
5.89	33.0	6.66	55.4
5.91	33.0	6.91	73.1
5.99	33.4	7.05	86.6
		7.25	108.6

Discussion

The Mechanism of the Dissociation Reaction :
The decomposition of chelates in acidic solution is generally considered to be stepwise as in equation (12) in which solvent molecules and most of the charges are omitted.

If stationary state kinetics are assumed for I equation (13) results

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k_1(k_2 + k_3[\text{H}^+])}{k_{-1} + k_2 + k_3[\text{H}^+]} \quad (13)$$

$$1/k_{obs} = \frac{1}{k_1} + \frac{k_{-1}}{k_1(k_2 + k_3[\text{H}^+])} \quad (14)$$

which, since k_2 can reasonably be taken to be much less than $k_3[\text{H}^+]$ and $\frac{k_1}{k_{-1}} = K_1$, can be written as

$$1/k_{obs} = \frac{1}{k_1} + \frac{1}{K_1 k_3[\text{H}^+]} \quad (15)$$

If stationary state kinetics are assumed for both II and III the result with $k_3/k_{-3} = K_3$ is

$$k_{obs} = \frac{k_1(k_2 + K_3 k_4[\text{H}^+])}{k_{-1} + k_2 + K_3 k_4[\text{H}^+]} \quad (16)$$

again neglecting k_2 equation (17) results

$$1/k_{obs} = \frac{1}{k_1} + \frac{1}{K_1 K_3 k_4[\text{H}^+]} \quad (17)$$

Equation (15) and (17) are of the form

$$1/k_{obs} = 1/k_1 + 1/C[\text{H}^+] \quad (18)$$

which was used above for data fitting. The ionic strength effect resides in k_3 ; k_1 is of course identical with the k_d used previously. Regardless of whether k_{obs} is given by equation (13) or equation (16) k_1 has the same meaning but C differs according to the details of the chosen mechanism. (In this paper the interpretation of C differs by a factor of k_1 compared with the one used previously¹). The Arrhenius parameters for the temperature variation of these rate constants are collected in Table 8.

TABLE 8—ARRHENIUS PARAMETERS FOR THE DISSOCIATION STEP

	A/sec ⁻¹	E _A /kcal
Ni (1-nitroso-2-naphthol)	1.48×10^{13}	13.2
Ni (1-nitroso-2-naphthol-6-sulphonate)	5.24×10^{15}	17.3
Ni (2-nitroso-1-naphthol-4-sulphonate)	1.86×10^8	7.79

The Arrhenius parameters in Table 8 are not as reliable as would be desired because the temperature range available experimentally is rather small. It would therefore be unwise to attribute too much significance to them at this time. It seems preferable to await further data on reactions of this type and then to examine any trends which may become apparent. It is worth noting however, that some of the reactions do have activation energies which are rather high.

The Ionic Strength Effect : According to the data in Table 6 only one reaction exhibits an ionic strength effect. For these reactions the effect of ionic strength on k_{obs} should be described by the general equation (19)

$$1/k_{obs} = 1/k_d + 1/(C^0[\text{H}^+]^{1+Q}) \quad (19)$$

where C^0 is the value of the relevant collection of constants at zero ionic strength and Q is the relevant function of the activities. In many cases it has been demonstrated that $Q = 2Z_A Z_B A I^{1/2} / (1 + I^{1/2})$ where A is the relevant Debye-Huckel coefficient. The data for the first and last compounds in Table 6 are expected to show no ionic strength effect in agreement with experiment. For Ni (1-nitroso-2-naphthol) Q is expected

to be $\frac{I^{1/2}}{1 + I^{1/2}}$. Using the data in Table 6 Figure 2

Figure 2. The Effect of Ionic Strength on the dissociation of Ni (1-nitroso-naphthol), $[H^+] = 0.02M$.

results showing excellent agreement with expectation with $2Z_A Z_B = 1$.

Equation (20) is a least squares fit of the form of equation (19) using these data

$$1/k_{obs} = 2.02 \times 10^{-3} + 2.54 \times 10^{-3} 10^Q \quad (20)$$

the standard deviations are 4.8×10^{-4} and 3.97×10^{-3} respectively.

From this equation k_a found to be 496 sec^{-1} is in very good agreement with the value of 489 in Table 4. As expected k_a is independent of ionic strength. Also C° is 1.97×10^3 . As a cross check the value of C° can be calculated from reciprocal of the slope for this reaction at $0.1 M$ ionic strength in equation (2) in reference 1, by solving the equation

$$C^\circ = 3.753 \times 10^3 \times 10^{1 + 0.1^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad (21)$$

This gives a value of 2.16×10^3 . The values of C° agree remarkably well (ca. 5%), and confirm that the ionic strength effect of the dissociation of Ni (1-nitroso-2-naphthol) is perfectly normal, as in two of the other three cases in Table 6.

Why then do the results for Ni(1-nitroso-2-naphthol-3,6-disulphonate) not exhibit the normal salt effect to be expected for a reaction of charge product $Z_A Z_B$

$= -1$? The nickel complex appears to behave in this reaction as though it possessed zero charge! That this unusual salt effect occurs only with the compound which is sulphonated in the 3-position indicates that we might be dealing with a strong H-bond as shown;

With reactions of this rapidity we have no way of examining the existence of the protonated species other than by kinetics. The effect might however also be observable in the free ligand. The pK_a value for the ionization

was found⁴ to be 7.54. We have more recently carefully examined potentiometric titration 'curves' in the pH region 2-9 looking for evidence of the ionization in equation (16)

The results were negative. NMR studies of the free ligand have yielded no evidence of significant shifts on acidification but the formation kinetics studies do provide support for the intervention of a second proton in the reaction sequence.

Formation Kinetics : If Ni^{2+} can react with both the species HL and L the rate equation can be written

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{[\text{Ni}]} \frac{d(\text{Products})}{dt} &= k_{obs} [\text{HL}]_{\text{total}} \\ &= k[\text{HL}] + k_2[\text{L}^-] \\ k_{obs} \frac{(\text{K}_a + \text{H}^+)}{\text{H}^+} &= k + \frac{k_2 k_a}{[\text{H}^+]} \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

where K_a is the acid dissociation constant for reaction (22). K_a has been measured for both ligands but under rather different experimental conditions, so the procedure adopted was as follows : The experimental data were fitted to equation (24) by the method of least squares iterating K_a until the best fit was obtained as measured by the minimum sum of squares of the residuals and shown by way of example in Figure 3.

Figure 3. Residuals obtained by iteration of K_a in equation (24) for the formation of Ni (2-nitroso-1-naphthol-4-sulphonate).

The resulting values (25°C) are

	K_a	k	k_2
2-nitroso-1-naphthol-4-sulphonate	4.0×10^{-7}	8.3 (1.7)	107 (.7)
1-nitroso-2-naphthol-3-6-sulphonate	$2. \times 10^{-8}$	30 (1)	286 (4)

the values in parenthesis are the standard deviations. The values for K_a are reasonable. In the case of the 2-nitroso-1-naphthol k agrees well with the observed values in acidic solution but k_{obs} shows a steady drift below k for 1-nitroso-2-naphthol-3-6-sulphonate which might again indicate an unusually strong hydrogen bridge between the proton and the substituents in the 2- and 3- positions. Efforts are now being made to obtain 1-nitroso-2-naphthol-3-sulphonate to examine this point.

Acknowledgement

We thank Dr. S. Bajue for the preparation and purification of 1-nitroso-2-naphthol-6-sulphonate and Mr. Roy Bailey for assistance with the computer analysis of the kinetics data.

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